

UN IMPLEMENTATION OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract This article covers seventeen global Goals adopted by the UN General Assembly and the role of these goals in the penetration and development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. We think that these goals apply to every citizen. These goals and objectives can be found out in our text below which millet is currently being implemented in our country.

Key words: Sustainable Development, Goals, UN, gender equality, clean energy, poverty reduction.

By the UN General Assembly, the 2015 Sustainable Development specific action plan, consisting of 17 goals and 169 tasks related to economic, social and environmental issues, was approved for 2030. When we talk about the penetration of these goals and objectives into our country, we can see on the basis of the action strategy for 2017-2021. The world community is widely recognized for the fact that the five directions of action strategy coincide with global goals.

Uzbekistan has repeatedly stated that it is also committed to achieving Sustainable Development Goals, and most importantly, it has promoted important initiatives towards achieving Sustainable Development Goals. In 2018, the Cabinet resolution “on measures to implement national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development in the period up to 2030” was adopted. Of the 17 Global Goals, 16 have been adopted domestically, and in 2018, 125 indicators for achieving sustainable development goals, i.e. target indicators, have now exceeded. It can be seen from this that our country is significantly developing in every possible way. A clear example of this is that we are ranked of 193 countries in the ranking of Sustainable Development Goals conducted by Germany's Bertslam Foundation. Citing sustainable development goals. Their 1st goal is to end extreme poverty. The essence of the goal is to end all forms of poverty until 2030. According to data, currently, 836 million people around the world still live in extreme poverty.

Ending hunger. To say the essence of this goal is to end hunger, ensure food security and improve nutrition and promote the sustainable development of Agriculture. Every ninth representative of the world population is not eating

enough food. It represents about 795 million people. Almost half of the mortality among children under 5 years of age, that is, 45%, is the result of malnutrition. Thus, 3.1 million children die each year.

According to World statistics, every yeti per second a person is losing his life from hunger. This means that we are now grateful to the conditions created for us and the favors that God has given us. Health and prosperity. The essence of this goal is to ensure a healthy lifestyle and promote the survival of people of all ages. It is important for each of us to make a thoughtful decision and start with our own health and the health of our loved ones by vaccinating our children in a timely manner, starting with support and protection measures. According to data, more than 6 million children under 5 years of age die every year. The fact that achieving health and prosperity will serve as one of the human rights, as well as the agenda of the sustainable development sector, is creating new opportunities to ensure that everyone, not only officials, uses the highest standards of the health and medical services sector.

Quality education. It is the essence of this goal to ensure inclusive, equal and quality education and to create an opportunity for continuing education for all. Currently, the number of children covered in primary school education in developing countries has reached 91%. The number of school-age children who do not attend school all over the world is 57 million. More than half of the children who do not attend school live in African countries south of the Sahara. According to data, 50% of these children live in areas affected by conflict typhoid. Education is an important link that allows you to achieve many other goals in the field of sustainable development. If there is an opportunity for quality education in humans, they will be able to get rid of the dust of helplessness. Therefore, education promotes the reduction of inequality and the achievement of gender equality.

Gender equality. Ensuring Gender equality is an extension of the rights and opportunities of all women and girls. In almost two-thirds of developing countries, gender equality has also been achieved in primary education in our country. Today, women make up at least 30 percent of the total in one chamber of the parliaments of 46 countries. To say the impact of Gender equality on women's lives, the lack of Education does not give way to professional training and has led to the limitation of opportunities in the labor market. The expansion of rights and opportunities for women and Girls plays an important role in accelerating economic growth and social rise. If women's Labor were fully

involved, the pace of rise would have increased in many countries, we think digan. In this case, the rise can increase by more than 10 percent in most cases.

Clean water and sanitation. Ensuring access to safe water reserves and sanitation facilities for all. Judging by the data, since the 90 s of the last century, 2.6 billion people have been enjoying clean water sources, but 663 million people still do not have such an opportunity. 2.4 billion people do not benefit from basic sanitation services such as toilets or adapted fossil pits. Nearly 1,000 children per day are losing their lives due to diarrheal diseases that can be prevented and corrected, causing problems in the water supply and sanitation sector. And this is a pity, it means that we use the blessings given to us by God wisely. Cheap and clean energy. Ensuring the possibility of using cheap, reliable, stable and modern sources of energy for all. Countries can accelerate the transition to a non-expensive, reliable and sustainable energetic system through investment in renewable energy sources, the use of more energy-efficient practices, as well as the use of clean energy-based technology and infrastructure. Not every fifth person in the world has access to electricity. About 3 billion people need conventional biomass, such as wood or plant residues, which are used for cooking and heating the House.

Industrialization, innovation and infrastructure. To create a solid infrastructure, to promote the introduction of a system enriched with extensive industrialization and innovation. Due to the rapid transformation of the Global economic landscape and the increase in inequality, the gradual growth is necessary to cover industrialization and, above all, opens the way for opportunities for all people. Secondly, it relies on innovation and reinforced infrastructure. It is not a secret for any of us that our country is currently doing extensive work in these areas.

Cooperation towards sustainable development. Activation of strengthening global cooperation in the interests of sustainable development. It is necessary for us to expel our government using actions to cooperate with business circles in order to achieve the goals of sustainable development. Currently, about 79% of the product imported by developing countries to developed countries is imported without customs duties. We hope that the life of our society will improve if we support the reforms that will be carried out in our country. It is necessary for us to bring them to the future generation in their entirety, while preserving the natural resources of our inhabited land. We must never forget that the future generation they have the right to live as well as we do.

References:

1. Nigmatov A., Pardayev F. Environmental safety and sustainable development. A guide to further training. - T.: TVPI publishing 2004.
2. Nigmatov A.N., Shivaldova N.S. Sultanov R.N. Environmental aspects of sustainable development guide. - T.: Bioecosan, 2004.
3. www.un.org/esa/sustdev/ - United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Commission site.
4. www.unesco.org -site of the UN organization for Educational, Scientific and cultural issues.

